

SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT OF THE QUALITY-OF-LIFE MODEL OF PEOPLE IN URBAN COMMUNITIES, THONBURI SIDE, BANGKOK

PAPHON WONGTRAKOOL¹, SUDA SUWANNAPIROM², WITHILAK CHANTANASOMBAT³ and NORAWAT CHAROEN RAJAPARK⁴

^{1,2,3,4} Development Administration, Graduate School, Suan Sunandha Rajabhat University.

Abstract

Bangkok is divided into 2 parts of the Chao Phraya River: the Phra Nakhon side and the Thonburi side. The Bangkok side is all about commercial districts and is the development of a business center, which is different and is the opposite of the Thonburi side, this creates a distinct niche of natural resource and human resources development. Therefore, it has caused problems and affected the context of the people of Thonburi. The objectives of this research are: 1) to study the level of the Sustainable Quality of Life of people in Urban Communities 2) To study the causal factors of urban development plan Economic Development Social Development and Environmental Dimension towards sustainable quality of life of people in Urban Communities and 3) To develop a Sustainable Quality of Life model of people in Urban Communities. It uses a combination of quantitative research and qualitative research. For quantitative research. The sample size is defined by 20 times the observed variables. Geospatial sampling uses questionnaires to collect data and analyze data with structural equation models. For qualitative research, data is collected by in-depth interviews with community chairs, 15 people. Use specific selection methods and analyze data with content-based analytics. The results showed that 1) Urban Development Plan, Economic Development, Social Development, Environmental Dimension and Sustainable Quality of Life of people in Urban Communities, have a high level of value 2(Urban Development Plan, Economic Development, Social Development and Environmental Dimension have a causal bishopric to Sustainable Quality of Life of people in Urban Communities and 3) Development of sustainable quality of life of people in Urban Communities. There are key elements linked from Economic Development to Urban Development Plan, to Social Development, and to Environmental Dimension. The ultimate goal is to ensure the sustainable quality of life of the people in the urban community. The findings suggest that economic development is fundamental to linking to various dimensions, with the ultimate goal being to ensure the quality of life of the people of the community, while simultaneously benefiting the general education scholars who have adopted the model to explain the phenomenon and learn it in the academic sphere in the future.

Keywords: Urban Development Plan / Economic Development / Social Development / Environmental Dimension / Sustainable Quality of Life of people in Urban Communities

INTRODUCTION

Bangkok is divided into 2 parts of the Chao Phraya River: the Phra Nakhon side and the Thonburi side. On the Bangkok side, there is a commercial and development district, a business center, with large-scale business mobility activities as the center of the job supply, the social and economic activities of the city today are therefore on the entire metropolitan side and there's a bit of a spread out on the Thonburi side, but it's not a big commercial district. Therefore, various forms of government and private development and projects are in the metropolitan area rather than the obvious, there may be housing projects, shopping centers, hypermarkets, some

community malls on the Thonburi side. But there are still smaller proportions. The fact that public and private development projects are taking place on the Bangkok side rather than improving infrastructure projects and improving the quality of life of people on the Thonburi side face structural problems and daily life. This creates a distinct niche in natural resource and human resource development (Surachet Kongcheep, 2020). According to a study on the quality of life of people living on the Thonburi side of Nithiphat Balsiri (2018), most development issues are still inferior to the Phra Nakhon side, the spatial income inequality is still high, with growth concentrated. Most citizens also have problems with access to public rights or welfare, enhancing good health, enhancing good education, or strengthening the provision of general social services to ensure the well-being of such citizens or improve their quality of life. In addition, there are important factors that affect the quality of life, such as economic conditions, housing and the environment, educational opportunities, physical health, mental health, Ability to pursue a career, Family relationships, social relationships and free time, strengthening to have a job, Income and community welfare. In the past, the Bangkok Authority has formulated a development roadmap, namely the Strategic Development Plan for Improving the Quality of Life of Citizens in the Bangkok Development Strategy of The Office of Strategy and Evaluation (M.P.P., p. 44) that sets out the 4th strategic plan to develop Bangkok into a city of good quality of life. But there are still problems with people's quality of life, and it's also a problem that's hard to solve. As a result, the researchers were interested in studying the sustainable quality of life of the people of Bangkok, especially in the Thonburi area. Therefore, the researchers defined the subject and conceptual framework of the research as "Sustainable Development of the Quality-of-Life Model of People in Urban Communities, Thonburi side, Bangkok".

LITERATURE REVIEW

Urban community

A community is inhabited by a certain number of people who are communicating with each other, have an idea, the same and different beliefs. Urban communities are classified as centers of prosperity and decline. A city is the location of various social organizations or entities, it is dense with population and is a gathering of people with ethnic differences, Ethnicity, religion and diverse in occupation, Education, Housing, Facilities, Environment and center of systems in all aspects. According to the Bangkok Regulation on Communities and Community Directors B.E. 2564 (2021, p. 10), "urban community" refers to a community with a relatively dense cluster of houses but not crowded. Utilities, public utilities and transportation are convenient. For the educational concept of Chaiyat Sirinsorn (2018, p. 15) defines urban community as It's an area with a certain amount of coexistence, and it has to be thick enough. It is an area with dense buildings in one of the subdivisions. Most people in the community have different occupations. There are various growths and degradations such as water pollution and environmental toxicity. Etc. As for the educational concept of Pramey (2021), it says that urban communities are indicative of densely populated areas, areas with basic needs, good resource area, the area has a lot of employment opportunities, and such an area can be considered as an area that meets the most basic needs that society should have for citizens or individuals.

Sustainable Quality of Life of people in Urban Communities (SUST)

Quality of life is a feature that explains the way of life, livelihood or lifestyle of the human being. And it may be said that quality of life is both good and bad, that doesn't meet the social benchmarks that are set. Quality of life meets the standard set forth is the quality of life that must meet the benchmark. In Thai society, basic necessity information criteria (EPA) have been used. Currently, in the National Economic and Social Development Plan No. 12 2017-2021, the benchmarks are set in 5 categories and 31 indicators (Hod District Community Development Bureau, 2018). And for sustainable quality of life of people in Urban Communities, based on the educational concept of Pongrat Bhiromrat, Ruldej Gertvichai and Nattapong Tesharatnaset (2020, p. 1494), Michelangeli (2015) has stated that a sustainable quality of life must be important in the development of factors such as economic, political, social, economic, and social. Environment, Education, Public Health, Justice. Because such factors are fundamental factors that will lead to fulfilling basic necessities, creating happiness, Satisfaction, Equality, Safety, Stability, etc. And such educational concepts are consistent with Zhan (1992, p. 179) addressing the quality of life in sustainable urban communities. There are criteria to consider: 1) life satisfaction; It is observed by the difference between intentional desire and success in life, in which how much a person is satisfied in life depends on the personality, character traits, Environment and Health Conditions 2) Feelings or self-confidence over a period of time as a matter of mental well-being, Self-esteem and self-image in that moment 3) Maintaining healthy, disease-free, and having the potential to successfully practice daily routines and 4) mental well-being that feels secure, Stable in life, Self-worth.

RESEARCH OBJECTIVES

- 1) To study the level of Sustainable Quality of Life of people in Urban Communities.
- 2) To study the causal factors of an urban development plan Economic Development Social Development and Environmental Dimension towards a sustainable quality of life of people in Urban Communities.
- 3) To develop a Sustainable Quality of Life model of people in Urban Communities.

RESEARCH HYPOTHESIS

- 1) Urban Development Plan, Economic Development, Social Development and Environmental Dimension, it has a direct influence on the Sustainable Quality of Life of people in Urban Communities.
- 2) Urban Development Plan, Economic Development and Social Development, it has a direct influence on the Environmental Dimension.
- 3) Urban Development Plan and Economic Development, it has a direct influence on Social Development.
- 4) The Urban Development Plan has a direct influence on Economic Development.

RESEARCH SCOPE

This study, define a mixed method is quantitative research to determine the influence of factors affecting the effectiveness of modern corporate management in rental apartments and qualitative research to support the effectiveness of modern corporate management, rental apartment housing.

Research Conceptual Framework

Figure 1: Modern organizational management enhancement patterns, apartment-rental housing

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

1. Quantitative Research

Samples Operators and 300 employees of rental apartments using a threshold of 20 times the observed variables (Grace, 2008, p. 15). Stratified sampling. The tool is the questionnaire. Analyze data with descriptive statistics and structural equation model analysis.

The tools used in the research are questionnaires on organizational management, building a customer base, selecting a value Occupancy behavior and the effectiveness of modern corporate management of apartment-for-rent housing, 75 items. 5-level estimation characteristics, individual IOC values equal to 0.67-1.00. The confidence of the entire questionnaire was .975. Analyze data using descriptive statistics and structural equation models to test the relationship between latent variables

and observed variables and the relationship between independent variables and variables followed by the LISREL program.

2. Qualitative Research

Key contributors include community presidents, including: 15 persons. The tool is a structured interview model, characteristics of open-ended questions. Collect data by in-depth interviews. Individual contributors of important information. Take the information obtained to analyze the content, categorization of reviews, organize primary and secondary issues to support quantitative research and create models for increasing the effectiveness of modern enterprise management, apartment-for-rent housing.

CONCLUSIONS

Based on the findings from this research. The study authors reported three objective findings and a structural equation model, in the following order:

- 1) The personal data of the respondents showed that the majority were male, representing 52.33 per cent. The majority of age groups were 41-50 years old, representing 23.33 per cent. For the majority of statuses in couple/marital status, 59.33 percent were in status. Most levels of education are on the secondary/diploma level. That's 37.33 percent. The majority of occupations were employed by company employees, accounting for 31.67 percent. The majority of monthly income is in the range of 10,001-20,000 Baht, which is 47.00 percent, and the majority of family members are in the 3rd level, which is 26.33 percent.
- 2) Summary of objective findings No. 1 to study the level of Sustainable Quality of Life of people in Urban Communities. In conclusion, the level of Sustainable Quality of Life of people in Urban Communities variables is high level. With the Economic Development (ECON) having an average of 4.25 percent, the highest. This was followed by Sustainable Quality of Life of people in Urban Communities (SUST) with an average of 4.13 per cent, Urban Development Plan (PLAN) with an average of 4.11 per cent, Social Development (SOCD) with an average of 4.05 per cent and Environmental Dimension (ENVI) with an average of 4.05 per cent respectively.
- 3) Summary of objective findings 2 to study the causal factors of the Urban Development Plan, Economic Development, Social Development, and Environmental Dimension on sustainable quality of life of people in Urban Communities.

Figure 1: Alternative relationship structure model (t-value)

The results analyzed the combined influences, direct influences, and indirect influences of alternative models.

Dependent Variables	Relationship	Independent Variables				R ²
		PLAN	ECON	SOCI	ENVI	
ECON	DE	0.63**	-	-	-	0.40
	IE	-	-	-	-	
	TE	0.63**	-	-	-	
SOCI	DE	0.17*	0.74**	-	-	0.64
	IE	0.47**	-	-	-	
	TE	0.64**	0.74**	-	-	
ENVI	DE	0.14*	0.35**	0.57**	-	0.77
	IE	0.54**	0.42**	-	-	
	TE	0.68**	0.77**	0.57**	-	
SUST	DE	0.18**	0.36**	0.67**	0.51**	0.94
	IE	0.43**	0.59**	0.29**	-	
	TE	0.61**	0.95**	0.96**	0.51**	

Chi-Square= 45.48, df=41, p-value = 0.291, GFI=0.98, AGFI=0.94, RMR=0.009, RMSEA=0.019, CFI=1.00, CN=423.39

Table 4.22 (continued)

R ² for Exogenous Variable						
	STRA	POLI	PROJ			
	0.79	0.93	0.57			
R ² for Endogenous Variable						
	OCCU	EARN	SAVI	EDUC	EQUA	PART
	0.70	0.75	0.86	0.74	0.83	0.82
R ² for Endogenous Variable						
	QUAL	GREE	VALU	BEIN	SAFE	OPUL
	0.70	0.83	0.76	0.62	0.72	0.75
R ² for Structural Equations						
	ECON	SOCI	ENVI	SUST		
	0.40	0.64	0.77	0.94		
Correlation Matrix Between Latent Variables						
	ECON	SOCI	ENVI	SUST	PLAN	
ECON	1.00					
SOCI	0.80	1.00				
ENVI	0.81	0.85	1.00			
SUST	0.71	0.92	0.90	1.00		
PLAN	0.63	0.57	0.55	0.62	1.00	

3.1 The correlational influence path can be described as an urban development plan (PLAN) with a direct impact on Economic Development (ECON) as much as 0.63. This was followed by sustainable quality of life of people in Urban Communities (SUST) of 0.18, Social Development (SOCI) at 0.17 and Environmental Dimension (ENVI) at 0.14, respectively. And indirectly affecting the environmental dimension (ENVI), Social Development (SOCI) and Sustainable Quality of Life of people in Urban Communities (SUST) was 0.54, 0.47 and 0.43, respectively.

3.2 It can be described as a pathway of influence on economic development (ECON) with a direct impact on Social Development (SOCI) as much as 0.74. This was followed by sustainable quality of life of people in Urban Communities (SUST) of 0.36 and Environmental Dimension (ENVI) of 0.35. And indirectly affecting the Sustainable Quality of Life of people in Urban Communities (SUST) and Environmental Dimension (ENVI) of 0.59 and 0.42, respectively.

3.3 Can explain the path of relationship influence that Social Development (SOCI) directly affects Sustainable Quality of Life of people in Urban Communities (SUST) as much as 0.67. This is followed by a direct result with the Environmental Dimension (ENVI) of 0.57 and the indirect effect on the Sustainable Quality of Life of people in Urban Communities (SUST) of 0.29.

3.4 The relationship influence pathway can be described as an environmental dimension (ENVI) directly affecting the Sustainable Quality of Life of people in Urban Communities (SUST) of 0.51.

4. To study to develop sustainable quality of life of people in Urban Communities. A summary of the findings from quantitative and qualitative research is as follows:

4.1 Quantitative Research Urban Development Plan Impact on Sustainable Quality of Life of people in Urban Communities Statistically significant at the level of 0.01. This can be interpreted as having implemented the Urban Development Plan more and more, resulting in sustainable quality of life of people in Urban Communities. Increased with. For Economic Development, it affects the Sustainable Quality of Life of people in Urban Communities. Statistically significant at the level of 0.01. This can be interpreted as when implemented in Economic Development. Increasingly, this will result in a Sustainable Quality of Life of people in Urban Communities. Add more too. For Social Development, it affects the Sustainable Quality of Life of people in Urban Communities. Statistically significant at the level of 0.01. Which can be interpreted as when social development. Increasingly, this will result in a Sustainable Quality of Life of people in Urban Communities. Add more too. And for Environmental Dimension, it affects the Sustainable Quality of Life of people in Urban Communities. Statistically significant at the level of 0.01. This can be interpreted as when performed in environmental dimensions. Increase this results in a Sustainable Quality of Life of people in Urban Communities. Add more too.

4.2 Quality Research Strategy, Policies and projects are elements of the implementation of the Urban Development Plan. Citizens in urban communities must participate in the formulation of the project, because each community has an idea, Beliefs, Culture, the context and needs that develop their own communities vary. From the occupational side, Income and savings are elements of Economic Development. People in communities of all genders, ages, will not be left out and must have collateral or benefits that create wealth in having savings, having an income and having a stable and secure career in the profession. Education, equity and participation are elements of Social Development. Improving the quality of life should be focused on the fundamentals of society or community: equality in human dignity. People in the community believe that equality is a continuation of sustainable participation and education. For environmental quality, being environmentally friendly and using resources in a meaningful way is an element of the Environmental Dimension. Improving the quality of life of people in urban communities requires sustainability in terms of environmental friendliness. People have a positive attitude towards life within the community, pay attention to the use of products that are produced from technology, pay attention to the impact on the environment, Care for the quality of the environment must be at a standard level or better than the standard. And for sustainable quality of life of people in Urban Communities. People within the community are career stable, Occupations are safe and meet the required standards.

DISCUSSION

1. Discuss the test results of structural model equations.

Strategy, Policies & Projects It's important to the Urban Development Plan Statistically significant at the level of 0.01. 79 percent, 93 and 57 percent of the relationships can be described, respectively. It can be explained that the policy approach affects the Urban Development Plan by the people in that particular community. Participating can determine how to improve one's own quality of life on their own.

Occupation, income and savings are statistically significant for Economic Development at 0.01. It can explain the relationship by 70 percent, 75 and 86 percent, respectively. It can be explained that having savings generated from having an income in a career plays an important role in ensuring the quality of life of people in urban communities.

Education, equity and participation were statistically significant for Social Development at 0.01. 74, 83 and 82 percent of the relationships can be described, respectively. And it can be explained that equality in living affects the improvement of the quality of life of people in urban communities, since when people have equality and equality in practice, existing inequality will decrease. The people in the community have a sense of self-worth and belonging to the community.

Environmental Quality, Environmental friendliness and knowledgeable use of resources are statistically significant for the Energy Dimension at 0.01. 70 percent, 83 and 76 percent of the relationships can be described, respectively. It can be explained that the environmental friendliness of people in urban communities affects the improvement of quality of life, both in the form of occupation and the utilization of consumables in their daily lifestyle.

Happiness, safety and security are statistically significant at 0.01. 62, 72 and 75 percent of the relationships can be described, respectively. And it can be explained that security affects the wellbeing of people in urban communities, stability in life and property, stability in having a consistent income, occupational stability, Health security and medical care

2. Discuss the value of theoretical concepts.

Being happy, safe and stable is statistically significant with the Sustainable Quality of Life of people in Urban Communities at 0.01. This is evidenced by its stability. There is a high level of value, followed by safety and happiness, respectively. This is consistent with qualitative findings that say that creating stability creates stability in life and property, such as occupational security, stability and advancement of mercenary careers, not being oppressed or being used unfairly, there is a reasonable wage or living expense to live. In addition, there should be stability in the property or finances, invest in yourself, build on the likes, set statements of expenses and savings, Economical use occurs, when necessary, there is a reserve emergency statement to pay, and there is the ability to clear debts and avoid having non-income debts. One important factor is that a good quality of life requires safety considerations for daily living both inside and outside the home, when a disaster occurs, it is possible to receive timely assistance or protection. And it is in line with the concept of Nattapol Sothiratviroj (2014) that

says that stability is a normal self-happiness. Emphasis on the social living conditions of man, reduce the risk of affecting human freedom and emphasizes human rights. Therefore, human security, thus highlights the potential to cope with recessions and recessions. This is in line with the concept of Manasvi Arjunaka (2019), which says that political stability is the stability created by government management. It is a policy that sets out the development plan so that the people of the country can live a good life in accordance with the basic standards prescribed, such as food security, water, shelter, having a job, earnings, having savings. And it covers intangible factors such as identity, acceptance, Participation and the right to self-government

SUGGESTIONS

1. The condition of the variables is found:

Findings and Suggestions 1

Findings: Based on the results of the analysis of variable conditions. Urban development plans affect the quality of life of people in urban communities sustainably. It was found that the policy had the greatest impact. It can be explained that the policy formulations imposed by the people, especially the people in the area, will have the greatest impact on improving the quality of life.

Suggestion: Policy formulation, a project or strategy should be started by the people of that community who take it seriously and sincerely.

Findings and Suggestions 2

Findings: Based on the results of the analysis of variable conditions. The economic dimension affects the quality of life of people in urban communities sustainably. It was found that saving money and having money generated from it affected the quality of life of a stable life. Therefore, having savings that come from having an income and a career is a sense of self-worth.

Suggestion: Agencies should take actions that focus on encouraging and encouraging people to have savings and savings. To create a sustainable and stable quality of life base.

Findings and Suggestions 3

Findings: Based on the results of the analysis of variable conditions. The social dimension affects the quality of life of people in urban communities sustainably. It was found that equality has the greatest impact. It explains that equality is fundamental to increasing equal access to public services and social welfare and condensing it to improving other areas of quality of life.

Suggestion: Various public and private agencies or organizations should take actions that focus on promoting the general public's awareness of equality as human beings.

Findings and Suggestions 4

Findings: Based on the results of the analysis of variable conditions. Environmental dimensions affect the quality of life of people in urban communities sustainably. It has been found that

being environmentally friendly has the greatest impact. It explains that the use of resources in everyday life within the community should be taken into account without causing an impact on the environment or causing minimal impact.

Suggestion: Create knowledge about environmentally friendly behaviors for the public to be continuously aware of, it must be adhered to as a community policy.

Findings and Suggestions 5

Findings: Based on the results of the analysis of variable conditions. Sustainable quality of life of people in urban communities it was found that stability has the greatest effect. It can be explained that any quality-of-life development must be aimed at ensuring stability in people's lives.

Suggestion: Stability in life is the ultimate goal. So, individuals, Family, Community, Society, the nation, and the people of the nation, must jointly create a common good without any hope for their own benefit until they forget to neglect the interests of the people next to them and the nation, etc.

2. Suggestions for future research

- 1) There should be educated on the issue of occupational security of citizens in the capital community.
- 2) There should be educated in the security of savings of citizens in urban or/and rural communities.
- 3) Education should be carried out in the safety of life and property of citizens in urban communities.
- 4) There should be a study of the desirable quality of life of young people. Cripple elder People experiencing social distress in Bangkok area
- 5) There should be structural studies of Thai society and security goals for the wellbeing of citizens.

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